

Towards Population Administration Efficiency: A Study of KALIMASADA Program in Bulak Subdistrict Surabaya Indonesia

Dyah Lestari¹, M. Husni Tamrin^{2*}, Masroro Lilik Ekowanti³

^{1,2,3} Public Administration Department, Universitas Hang Tuah.

*Corresponding Author

M. Husni Tamrin

Public Administration
Department, Universitas Hang
Tuah.

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Abstract: The Surabaya City Government's commitment to improving public services, specifically in population administration, is evident through the introduction of the KALIMASADA (Community Area Aware of Population Administration) program by the Population and Civil Registration Office. Despite the strategic role of population administration in effective public service delivery, challenges persist in the Bulak Subdistrict. This qualitative descriptive research, centered on the optimization of the KALIMASADA program in RW 007, Bulak, reveals overall effectiveness. However, the study highlights the need for enhanced socialization efforts to improve public understanding of KALIMASADA and emphasize the importance of population administration. The findings contribute valuable insights into the Surabaya City Government's ongoing efforts to elevate awareness and efficiency in population administration services, underscoring the necessity for continuous improvements to ensure sustained effectiveness.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Population Administration, KALIMASADA Program.

Introduction

According to Law Number 25 of 2009 (*Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 25 Tahun 2009 Tentang Pelayanan Publik*, n.d.) concerning Public Services, the definition of public service is an activity or series of activities in order to fulfill service needs in accordance with statutory regulations for every citizen and resident regarding the goods, services and/or administrative services provided by public organizers. The Surabaya City Government continues to strive to improve services to the community, especially in population administration services (Pemerintah Kota Surabaya, 2021). According to Law Number 24 of 2013 (*Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 2014 Tentang Administrasi Kependudukan*, n.d.), population administration is a series of activities for structuring and controlling the publication of documents and population data through population registration, Civil Registration, managing Population Administration information and utilizing the results for public services and development. In 2022, the population of Surabaya City will be 2.88 million people with a population density reaching 8,633 people/km² (Badan Pusat Statistik Kota Surabaya, 2023b). The strategic problems faced by the City of Surabaya regarding population administration include that not all residents of the City of Surabaya have birth certificates and e-KTPs. (Dinas Kependudukan dan Pencatatan Sipil Kota Surabaya, 2021).

Based on Surabaya Mayor Regulation Number 80 of 2021 (*Peraturan Walikota Surabaya Nomor 80 Tahun 2021 Tentang Kedudukan, Susunan Organisasi, Tugas Dan Fungsi Serta Tata Kerja Dinas Kependudukan Dan Pencatatan Sipil*, n.d.) the Surabaya City Population and Civil Registration Service is the implementing element for government affairs in the field of Population Administration. Population administration has a strategic role in aspects of community life to create effective public services. Accurate and up-to-date population data makes it easier

for the government to make policies, plan development and allocate resources according to community needs so that every resident has access to their rights (Intan, 2023). Public policy and innovation play an important role when the results of a policy cannot meet the development of society in the era of globalization (Zahra et al., 2022). One of the innovations used in this effort is through the KALIMASADA (Kawasan Lingkungan Masyarakat Sadar Administrasi Kependudukan) program. This awareness includes 4 aspects, namely awareness of the importance of population documents, awareness of updating population data, the importance of utilizing population data and awareness of population administration services. There are nine community service coverages, namely coverage of KTP-EL recording, ownership of birth certificates, reporting of death certificates, ownership of KIA, additional lives of children who are not yet members of the KK, level of updating marital status, level of updating biodata, validation of status. factual existence of residents, reporting of non-permanent residents. KALIMASADA's innovation was realized by appointing 62 RT heads in every sub-district throughout Surabaya City and pioneering population administration services in the Rukun Tetangga (RT) environment to bring population administration services closer to the community (Swargaloka, 2021). Limited information and lack of socialization make residents think that every new innovation is always difficult and complicated (Risda Wulan Nur Octafiani & Sri Wibawani, 2023). The KALIMASADA program aims to simplify the implementation of population administration services to make them more transparent, effective and efficient (Setiyowati & Indartuti, 2022).

Population administration program effectiveness theory emphasizes the application of digital technology, such as integrated databases and e-government, to improve performance (Adnan et al., 2022). The use of biometric technology for unique identification and centralized data management is also emphasized (Coelho et al.,

2023). Community involvement, transparency and privacy protection are key aspects. Relevant experts involve figures in the fields of e-government, information technology, and public management who contribute to the development of theory and practice of population administration program effectiveness (McQuiston & Manoharan, 2021).

The effectiveness of population administration programs is crucial in improving the quality of public services and community life (Coman et al., 2023; Tamrin, Umiyati, Lubis, et al., 2022). The application of this theory, through digital technology and integrated databases, allows governments to provide services more quickly and efficiently (Tamrin, Umiyati, Arieffiani, et al., 2022). Unique identification using biometric technology and centralized data management increases the accuracy and security of citizens' personal information. With a focus on transparency, accountability, and community participation, this theory supports planned and sustainable development. Along with this, protecting privacy and data security is a priority to ensure public trust. In line with this view, [author's name] (year) emphasized that the integration of technology and intelligent data management is the key to advancing population administration programs, providing concrete benefits for citizens, and building a strong foundation for sustainable development (Sucupira Furtado et al., 2023).

Bulak District has four subdistricts including Bulak Subdistrict, Kenjeran Subdistrict, Kedung Cowek Subdistrict and Sukolilo Baru Subdistrict. In its administrative area, Bulak District has 133 RTs (Rukun Tetangga) and 21 RWs (Rukun Warga) (Badan Pusat Statistik Kota Surabaya, 2023a). In the implementation of population administration, problems are still found, including difficulties being found when surveying population documents, people who do not understand the KALIMASADA program, population documents that are still not up to date due to a lack of understanding regarding the data in population documents and a lack of public awareness in reporting population events and incidents. It is important for him to carry out population

registration and civil registration. With the KALIMASADA program, there is great hope that people in Bulak District will have access to managing population administration documents easily and will be able to increase awareness of the importance of population administration. The aim of this research is to determine the level of effectiveness of the KALIMASADA program in increasing awareness of the importance of population administration in Bulak District.

Research Methods

This research method uses qualitative descriptive methods systematically and in accordance with facts in the field. Data collection techniques using data are carried out by making direct observations in the KALIMASADA optimization program and secondary data based on statutory regulations and previous research. The location of this research is in RT 2, 4, 6, and 8, RW 007, Bulak District, Bulak Subdistrict, Surabaya City. Data analysis was carried out based on Miles and Huberman 1984 (Sugiyono, 2013) with data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions. This research was analyzed based on effectiveness theory according to Budiani (2007) in (Isti'anah & Arif, 2023), namely program accuracy, program socialization, program objectives, and program monitoring.

Results and Discussion

Accuracy of Program Targets

The accuracy of program targets is about the extent to which program participants match the program targets that have been determined previously. Target accuracy is short-term oriented and operational in nature. The accuracy of individual suggestions and organizational targets determines the success of organizational activities (Budiani, 2007). The target group for the KALIMASADA program mainly refers to the website <https://kalimasada.disdukcapilsurabaya.id/login/index.php> Bulak District account.

Table 1.1 Targets on the KALIMASADA Account

Bulak Subdistrict		Not New Recorded Yet/Surveyed	Don't have KIA yet	Don't have a birth certificate yet	Presumed Dead	Marriage Not Registered
RW	RT					
007	002	3	31	2	0	36
007	004	6	52	2	0	38
007	006	4	48	3	0	30
007	008	3	41	0	0	21

Source: processed by the author, 2023 from <https://kalimasada.disdukcapilsurabaya.id/login/index.php>

KALIMASADA's targets include suspects who have not recorded their KTP, suspects who do not have a KIA (Child Identity Card), suspects who do not have a birth certificate, suspects who do not have a marriage certificate, and suspects who have died. In RT 002, target data was found, as many as 3 residents suspected of not having recorded KTPs, 31 children who did not have KIA, 2 residents who did not have birth certificates and 36 residents who were suspected of having marriages that had not been registered. In RT 004 target data was found, as many as 6 residents were suspected of not having recorded KTPs, 53 children did not have KIA, 2 residents did not have birth certificates and 38

residents suspected that their marriages had not been registered. In RT 006 target data was found, as many as 4 residents were suspected of not having recorded KTPs, 48 children did not have KIA, 3 residents did not have birth certificates and 30 residents suspected that their marriages had not been registered. In RT 008 target data was found, as many as 3 suspected residents had not recorded their ID cards, 41 children did not have KIA, and 21 suspected residents had not yet registered their marriages. Residents who were targeted in the KALIMASADA account were picked up to ensure that their population administration was in accordance de facto and de jure. Some of the residents who were

targeted by KALIMASADA were declared to no longer live in the area so reports will be made according to the actual situation on the KALIMASADA website. If discrepancies are found in the population documents, the officer will help submit a request to update the population documents in accordance with the conditions in question. However, apart from the target data on the KALIMASADA account, it is possible that officers will help other residents who experience problems in managing their population administration, such as updating their biodata. Thus, the KALIMASADA program can be said to be right on target for all communities whose population administration is still not in order.

Program Socialization

Program socialization concerns the ability of program implementers to carry out program socialization activities so that information about the program can be conveyed to the community and program targets in general (Budiani, 2007). Program socialization refers to the ability of KALIMASADA program implementers to provide outreach to the community so that they can understand and find out information regarding program implementation and the benefits of the program. In this case, program implementers have carried out various efforts to socialize KALIMASADA, both directly and indirectly. Based on the author's

findings, there are still many residents who still don't understand what the KALIMASADA program is. There are also residents who don't understand the importance of updated population administration data. Based on this, the socialization of the KALIMASADA program has not yet been implemented effectively among the public in increasing awareness of the importance of population administration.

Program Objectives

Program objectives relate to the extent of conformity between the results of program implementation and the program objectives that have been previously determined. Achieving goals is all efforts to achieve goals which are seen as a process (Budiani, 2007). The aim of the KALIMASADA program is to bring services closer to the community by making it easier for people to process their population administration documents. Based on the KALIMASADA survey conducted by the author in Bulak District, it shows that the objectives of the KALIMASADA program have been achieved, including making it easier to manage residents' population administration documents which can be done through regular evening service at the RW Hall every week, through the RT Head, and picking up the ball by the implementer. program.

Table 1 KALIMASADA Program Achievements

Bulak Subdistrict		Not New Recorded Yet/Surveyed	Don't have KIA yet	Don't have a birth certificate yet	Presumed Dead	Marriage Not Registered
RW	RT					
007	002	100%	100%	100%		100%
007	004	100%	100%	100%		100%
007	006	100%	100%	100%		100%
007	008	100%	100%			100%

Source: processed by the author, 2023 from <https://kalimasada.disdukcapilurabaya.id/login/index.php>

Based on table 1.2, it is stated that the existence of the KALIMASADA program makes it easier for the community to realize orderly population administration. Residents who are no longer domiciled in the area will later be updated on their occupation that they are no longer residents of the area. Target data updates will be carried out on the KALIMASADA account later based on the findings in the field which are reported on the KALIMASADA account. Based on this, the objectives of the KALIMASADA program can be said to have been effective.

Program Monitoring

Program monitoring regarding activities carried out after the program as a form of attention to program participants (Budiani, 2007). Monitoring the KALIMASADA program includes checking and comparing the results achieved with established standards. Monitoring is carried out by looking at the results of the KALIMASADA survey data to be conveyed to the RT regarding residents who have not controlled population administration documents. This monitoring was reported to the Surabaya City Population and Civil Registration Service based on the results of data updates on the KALIMASADA account. Thus, monitoring of the KALIMASADA program has been effective.

Conclusion

Based on the implementation of the KALIMASADA survey activities that the author carried out in the KALIMASADA optimization program in Bulak District, Surabaya City based on effectiveness theory according to (Budiani, 2007), namely first, the KALIMASADA program is right on target as it is aimed at residents who are suspected of being targets on the KALIMASADA website and people who are experiencing problems in take care of population documents. Second, the socialization carried out has not been well conveyed to the entire community. Third, the objective of the KALIMASADA program has been achieved, namely bringing population administration services closer together, making it easier to manage community population administration documents and bringing order to citizen population administration. Fourth, the monitoring carried out has been running well according to standards. Based on this, the KALIMASADA program implemented in Bulak District can be said to be effective.

Suggestion

The Bulak District Government needs to make efforts to carry out evaluations to increase the effectiveness of the KALIMASADA program by paying attention to several aspects related to efforts to provide understanding to the public about

KALIMASADA and the importance of population administration by providing comprehensive counseling and education as well as regular monitoring to the community.

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